

METHODS OF IMPROVING THE MUSICAL COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS THROUGH CHILDREN'S CENTERS

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Annotatsiya: This article discusses the theoretical significance of independent thinking in the formation of musical creativity of students. The role of the pedagogical staff in the formation of creative abilities is also described.

Keywords: creativity, independent thinking, music culture, pedagogue, education system, student.

Teaching the young generation to independent and creative thinking and creativity is one of the most urgent tasks of Uzbek pedagogy during the independence period. In this way, finding new and effective ways to teach students to think independently and creatively is important not only for the development of teaching methods, but also for the realization of a well-rounded personality.

In the scientific literature created so far, there are different views on teaching musical students to think independently and creatively. For example, according to some scientists, the process of teaching students to draw correct conclusions from various scientific information by developing their ability to understand their knowledge is important for the formation of creative thinking skills. The important part of this theory is that it can be used in all kinds of musical training.

According to the well-known methodologists of musical education, it is recommended to first choose a repertoire for students to listen to, select a specific piece of music, and show an exemplary performance of the selected piece. However, scientists have neglected the fact that the student's performance should be compared with the performance of the model and the necessary advice should be given to the student. In our opinion, when the student performs a musical piece from the selected repertoire, each part of the piece should be compared step by step with the model performance. Only then will the student overcome his shortcomings.

Ways to increase students' creative activity in music lessons.

As we increase music education in general education schools, the teacher has the task of arousing students' interest in their lesson and music. In school, especially in elementary grades, the interest and inclination towards singing, listening to music, gradually plays an important role in the development and formation of young people's positive attitude towards art and their needs. A music lesson is an art lesson by its nature. Its colorful and interesting organization requires great pedagogical and professional skills from every teacher. It is extremely difficult to teach children to art, the whole complexity is that it is absolutely impossible to teach them true art without engaging them emotionally.

In this place, it is of particular importance to ensure the creative activity of students during musical lessons. Understanding music and enjoying its relaxing effect depends on the participation of emotional feelings as well as knowledge, skills and abilities. The more active and deep the emotions are in the performance and perception of the work, the more

conscious and deep their understanding and mastering, satisfaction and enjoyment will be. These situations are a process that occurs as a result of creative activity. Because the state of dullness and silence cannot create a state of lively emotions in the classroom. Attracting students to the lesson is primarily related to the repertoire of works to be listened to for listening and performance. The main criterion of the repertoire of works selected for elementary classes is determined by the youth of the students, their interests and the level of knowledge and skills, the color and diversity of the subject, the ideological and artistic quality, and the pedagogical value. In other words, the school reflects the highest ideas and images of the past and present, which are suitable for the youth and perceptive abilities of the students, and are beautiful and life-giving, elegant and elegant in their form and content. works should be played. After all, only these works can arouse students' interest and enthusiasm for the lesson, develop their moral-aesthetic feelings and necessary skills.

Pupils' interest in the lesson depends on how interesting, meaningful, and understandable the lessons are, as well as on the variety of materials. The lessons, which are rich in musical pieces, various visual aids, interesting facts and information about music, and are organized at a steady pace from the beginning to the end, make a great impression on the students.

The current era is a time when ideological contradictions in the world have become complex, and ideological camps are becoming stronger than nuclear training camps. That is why all means are being used to educate the young generation in the spirit of national consciousness and national ideology. In this regard, the art of music, especially singing, combines two great arts - poetry and music, and becomes a great educational tool.

In different methodical sources, there are different views on teaching musical students to creative thinking and creativity. For example, according to some experts, the process of teaching children to draw correct conclusions from various scientific information is important for the formation of creativity. The importance of this theory is that it can be used in all kinds of musical training.

The activity of musical creativity is of great importance for the development of musical thinking, research and creativity in children. One of the most convenient ways to find students in music lessons is to use the method of performance and comparison in music lessons, which is done as follows. For this, it is necessary for the music teacher to conditionally divide the music lessons into groups, taking into account the effect on the education of the student. When grouping music lessons, it is necessary to take into account the attitude of the student to the background of music. If approached from this point of view, the component of the lesson: listening to music, then music literacy will also consist of performance and comparison. Especially at the performance and comparison stage of the lesson, the student's knowledge of the subject is checked. The performance of the work is performed by the student. It is necessary to compare the performance of the student with the performance of the sample and analyze its achievements and shortcomings. Approaching music education in this way encourages the learner to work independently, to think independently about the studied piece, to approach the performance of a musical piece creatively.

The activity of musical creativity is very important to pay attention to talented and talented students in the class and to satisfy their artistic needs. Timely manifestation of talent depends on education and support. It is necessary to analyze the abilities of young people to show their talent, to take into account the unique qualities of the child, to effectively implement the

development of creative abilities. Levels and stages of development of abilities will be related to new relationships.

A certain level of musical ability can be formed in any student. This is developed in the conditions of organized musical education and educational process. In order to develop the musical ability of young students, to consciously stimulate talent and talent, to create conditions for excellence, to further develop their relationship to the art of music, to participate in various art events, Olympiads, art festivals. , should be involved in competitions, meetings. The activity of musical creativity is performed by the music teacher, with creative practices such as clicking accompaniment, finding actions suitable for the melody of the recommended melody, composing a melody for the given poem. When a music teacher plays a piece of music, it starts with learning to accompany the circle with a clap. Later, after learning to play with percussion instruments such as spoon and safoil, a child who is a clapper learns to play with a circle and tries to join in the performance of the piece.

During the performance of a song, the teacher usually emphasizes the work with his hand movements, i.e. moving his hand downwards to show a strong part, and up to a weak part, he sings. Children can show their talents by conducting another work similar to this movement. It is necessary to explain to the students the work of the conductor, who is watching the actions of the child, and that for this he must study a lot and have good musical knowledge. It is necessary for the music teacher to have a positive attitude towards the melody, song, dance created by the children, to the issue of music literacy, to support and encourage their creativity. All this helps to increase children's love for the art of music.

The interaction between the teacher and the student in the music lesson is based on personal communication. The music teacher directs and supervises the musical activities of all students in the lesson without exception. Also, it supports communication and mutual control among students. The work of the teacher in the lesson creates the ground for all students to acquire the basics of knowledge, to develop the necessary skills and qualifications in the lesson itself. A music lesson gives a feeling of understanding the joy of music creation. It forms the ability to enjoy the moral-aesthetic content of the composer or folk music. In the lesson, all types of creative activity, which are strongly connected with each other, will be effective.

At the same time, it is necessary that the lesson, with its content, methods, and organization, should have an educational impact on the students and have a great educational value by forming their scientific worldview, ideological belief, and moral qualities of the individual. Education, training, development, creative development, teaching of students should be carried out together and in interaction. We are one of the most important principles of music pedagogy.

The school prepares students for professional musical activity. However, the ability to understand music, perceive it and be creatively influenced by it is essential to every student, whether he will be a professional musician in the future or a musical culture in various forms of musical-aesthetic activity, skills and competences. Regardless of whether it will be a well-prepared trigger, it should be unique.

Currently, the requirements for music lessons are as follows.

1. provides for the comprehensive implementation of the functions of education, development and training in music lessons. It affects all aspects of the student's formation. Along with improving the student's musical knowledge, it develops mental power and abilities, increases

performance culture and creative potential, develops worldview, moral, aesthetic and willful qualities, attitude to work.

2. The lesson is conducted according to a strict system according to the form of the lesson: it consists of a certain beginning, defining the goals and tasks of the lesson, explaining, consolidating and repeating the musical material, giving homework. Types of musical activities should be interconnected and complement each other.

3. the lesson is in accordance with the principles of teaching: it has an educational effect, it is convenient for scientific understanding, it helps to master musical works in a thorough and conscious way, to form musical skills and abilities, and to create freely.

In addition to teaching, music lessons also include educational goals and tasks. They are determined by the content of educational materials, as well as by the general goals aimed at educating and improving the personality of schoolchildren, educational tasks may be related to the formation of moral, voluntary intellectual, emotional qualities of a person. The lesson is a specific stage in the continuous process of educating students.

The unique aspect of the music lesson is that, in addition to the tasks of music education, the tasks of artistic creativity are also set in the lesson. First of all, it refers to group singing, which is an active form of music education at school. Singing as a group with deep folk traditions develops not only musical abilities, but also character quality, outlook, artistic taste, fantasy, and aesthetic sense. Singing in a group combines various forms of work in the class, singing, musical literacy, understanding of music, playing to music, vocal creativity,

Understanding the content of a piece of music depends on the general culture of the listener, as well as his special preparation, and special preparation in turn affects the active level of listening attention. It is well known that listeners who are trained in music have better perception. A student who understands music is distinguished by a high level of artistic talent, having a great experience as a listener based on understanding the specific nature of the musical form, its content, the history of the development of music, and having developed skills and qualifications in the field of musical-creative activity. A piece of music can be fully understood only on the basis of listening.

It is also necessary to know that it is very important for the teacher to have his own reputation. In all classes, students look at their teachers with a critical eye. If they respect others, they don't respect others because they don't have these characteristics. If a music teacher plays a musical instrument attractively, sings a song pleasantly, fascinates children with stories about music genres and composers, plays his role as a teacher in a 45-minute lesson, he is creative and positive with children in all subjects. If he can establish relationships and find his way into the hearts of the children, such a teacher will be loved by children.

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